

An Exact Modal Impedance Boundary Condition for Finite Element Simulation of Local Seismic Response

¹Faustino Cetraro

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Abstract

In this work, an impedance-based non-reflecting boundary condition for finite element simulations of elastodynamic wave propagation is presented. The proposed method, referred to as the Adaptive Boundary Mode–Impedance Boundary Condition (ABM-IBC), is derived from the exact Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) map of an elastic half-space and implemented through a local modal decomposition of the wavefield along the computational boundary.

The formulation is developed for two-dimensional isotropic elastodynamics and explicitly accounts for both propagating and evanescent modes associated with compressional (P) and vertically polarized shear (SV) waves. For each horizontal wavenumber, the exact dynamic impedance of the elastic half-space is evaluated in modal space and applied to the boundary velocities, while the corresponding physical tractions are reconstructed through an efficient inverse spectral transform.

The proposed boundary condition is implemented in a time-domain finite element framework using a local spectral decomposition of boundary velocities and a fast Fourier transform (FFT)-based reconstruction of boundary tractions. Unlike absorbing layer techniques such as Perfectly Matched Layers (PML) and Convolutional PML (C-PML), the ABM-IBC operates directly on the physical boundary, does not require additional computational domains or auxiliary variables, and introduces no parameters to be calibrated.

Numerical simulations representative of local seismic response analyses demonstrate that the proposed formulation significantly reduces spurious boundary reflections, particularly for oblique and near-grazing wave incidence, while preserving numerical stability and reducing computational cost when compared with classical PML-based approaches.

Keywords: Impedance boundary condition; Dirichlet-to-Neumann map; elastodynamic wave propagation; finite element method; seismic wave absorption; local seismic response; modal decomposition.

¹ Faustino Cetraro – Geologist and author of technical and professional books, as well as developer of specialized software in the fields of geotechnics, hydrogeology, and hydraulics. Publications available on [engeosoil](https://engeosoil.altervista.org).

1. Introduction

The numerical simulation of seismic wave propagation in finite geotechnical models requires the adoption of boundary conditions capable of accurately reproducing the radiative behavior of an elastic half-space. In the absence of suitable non-reflecting boundary conditions, waves reaching the artificial boundaries of the computational domain are partially reflected, introducing numerical artifacts that may compromise the interpretation of the local seismic response.

The techniques most commonly employed within the finite element method (FEM) framework are based on absorbing layers, such as Perfectly Matched Layers (PML) and their convolutional extensions (C-PML). Although widely used, these formulations exhibit several well-known limitations, including the need to introduce an additional artificial domain, dependence on damping parameters that require calibration, an increase in the total number of degrees of freedom, and a loss of effectiveness in the presence of strongly oblique or nearly grazing incident waves.

A conceptually more rigorous alternative is provided by boundary conditions based on the Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) map, which yields the exact relationship between displacements (or velocities) and tractions at the boundary of an elastic half-space. However, the direct implementation of DtN operators is often hindered by high computational complexity, particularly in time-domain formulations, or by the requirement for analytical solutions restricted to simple geometries.

Within this context, the present work introduces a formulation referred to as the **Adaptive Boundary Mode-Impedance Boundary Condition (ABM-IBC)**. The proposed approach combines a local modal decomposition of the elastodynamic field along the boundary with the computation of the exact dynamic impedance of the elastic half-space for each mode, followed by the reconstruction of the physical tractions to be applied at the FEM boundary nodes.

The objective of this study is to rigorously formulate the ABM-IBC, describe its numerical implementation within an explicit FEM framework, and assess

its performance in the context of local seismic response simulations, through a systematic comparison with conventional PML and C-PML formulations.

2. Theoretical foundations of modal absorption

2.1 Modal representation of the elastodynamic field

Consider a two-dimensional isotropic elastic medium (P–SV motion) occupying the half-space $y \geq 0$, bounded by a planar boundary Γ parallel to the x -axis. The reference coordinate system is defined such that the x -axis is tangential to the boundary, while the y -axis is normal to it. In the vicinity of the boundary, the displacement field can be represented as a continuous superposition of harmonic plane-wave modes characterized by the horizontal wave-number k_x :

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{\mathbf{u}}(k_x) e^{i(k_x x - \omega t)} e^{iqy} dk_x \quad (1)$$

where:

- ω is the angular frequency,
- q is the vertical wavenumber, which is a function of k_x and the type of wave.

For an isotropic medium, the vertical components of the wavenumbers for compressional (P) waves and vertically polarized shear (SV) waves are given by:

$$q_P \sqrt{\left(\frac{\omega}{c_P}\right)^2 - k_x^2}, \quad q_S \sqrt{\left(\frac{\omega}{c_S}\right)^2 - k_x^2} \quad (2)$$

where c_P and c_S are the P-wave and S-wave velocities, respectively.

The roots of expressions (2) are chosen by imposing the radiation condition, which requires $Im(q_P) \geq 0$ and $Im(q_S) \geq 0$.

Modes for which $|k_x| < \omega/c$ (with $c = c_P$ or c_S) are propagating, whereas those for which $|k_x| > \omega/c$ are evanescent and decay exponentially with distance from the boundary.

2.2 P and SV Modes and Polarization

In the two-dimensional P–SV case, the elastodynamic field can be expressed as a linear combination of the contributions associated with compressional

(P) waves and vertically polarized shear (SV) waves. For each horizontal wavenumber k_x , the vertical dependence of the displacement field can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}(y) = A_P \mathbf{p}_P e^{iq_P y} + A_S \mathbf{p}_{SV} e^{iq_S y} \quad (3)$$

where A_P and A_S are the modal amplitudes associated with the P and SV contributions, respectively, while q_P and q_S are the vertical wavenumbers defined in Eq. (2). The harmonic dependence along the x -axis and in time, $e^{i(k_x x - \omega t)}$, is implied.

The polarization vectors \mathbf{p}_P and \mathbf{p}_{SV} describe the particle motion direction associated with each wave type and are defined as:

$$\mathbf{p}_P = \frac{1}{\omega} \begin{bmatrix} k_x \\ q_P \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{p}_{SV} = \frac{1}{\omega} \begin{bmatrix} q_S \\ -k_x \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In the case of P waves, the polarization vector is parallel to the wavenumber vector, indicating a predominantly longitudinal motion. For SV waves, the polarization vector is orthogonal to the wavenumber vector in the x - y plane, corresponding to a vertically polarized shear motion.

The polarization vectors \mathbf{p}_P e \mathbf{p}_{SV} are orthogonal in the energetic sense, meaning that the energy fluxes associated with the P and SV contributions are mutually decoupled. This property allows the two wave types to be treated separately in the modal formulation and forms the basis for constructing the dynamic impedance of the elastic half-space.

2.3 Dirichlet-to-Neumann Map

The ideal non-reflecting boundary condition for an elastic half-space consists of imposing, on the boundary Γ u a local relation in modal space between the traction $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the particle velocity $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{Z}(k_x, \omega) \dot{\mathbf{u}} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{Z}(k_x, \omega)$ is the dynamic impedance matrix of the elastic half-space. It represents the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastodynamic problem in the modal and frequency domain, as it provides the exact relation between the kinematic quantities (displacements or velocities) and the tractions acting on the boundary.

For each mode characterized by k_x , the impedance matrix can be derived from the elastic constitutive relations and the equations of motion, yielding a

closed-form expression as a function of the density ρ , the wave velocities c_P and c_S , the angular frequency ω and the vertical wavenumbers q_P and q_S . This formulation naturally accounts for both propagating and evanescent modes. A fundamental property of the matrix \mathbf{Z} is that it ensures the energetic passivity of the boundary condition. The time-averaged power flux through the boundary can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{P} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(\dot{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the conjugate transpose. Inequality (6) ensures that the boundary condition correctly reproduces the radiative behavior of the elastic half-space and is intrinsically stable in the continuous setting.

2.4 Remarks on the Continuous Formulation

In the continuous setting and in modal representation, the exact imposition of the impedance relation (5) is mathematically equivalent to enforcing the radiation condition of the elastic half-space. In this formulation, for each horizontal wavenumber k_x the traction applied on the boundary exactly reproduces the behavior of an outgoing wave, ensuring the absence of modal reflections in the continuous limit. Consequently, in the continuous domain and for a single harmonic mode, the modal reflection coefficient associated with condition (5) is theoretically zero. This property provides the theoretical foundation for boundary conditions based on the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map. In the discrete numerical context, however, the absorption accuracy is no longer exact and depends on factors such as the spectral resolution of the boundary, the quality of the spatial discretization, and the accurate representation of both propagating and evanescent modes. The impact of these factors on the numerical response will be analyzed in the following sections dedicated to implementation and results.

3. Mathematical Formulation of the ABM-IBC

3.1 General Concept

The *Adaptive Boundary Mode-Impedance Boundary Condition* (ABM-IBC) is a non-reflecting boundary condition that implements the Dirichlet-to-Neumann

map of the elastic half-space in a numerically efficient way within finite element elastodynamic simulations. The underlying principle of the method consists of applying the exact dynamic impedance of the half-space in modal space, where the relation between velocity and traction is rigorously satisfied for each horizontal wavenumber.

Specifically, the kinematic field along the boundary is first decomposed into modal contributions, for each of which the corresponding dynamic impedance is evaluated. The physical traction to be applied at the FEM boundary nodes is then reconstructed via an inverse transform, ensuring a consistent representation of the radiative behavior of the elastic half-space.

The approach operates entirely on the physical boundary of the computational domain and does not require the introduction of additional artificial domains or auxiliary variables, as is the case with formulations based on absorbing layers (e.g., PML and C-PML). This allows for a reduction in overall computational cost and avoids the need to tune empirical parameters, while maintaining high accuracy in the absorption of incident waves.

3.2 Local Modal Decomposition along the Boundary

Consider the boundary Γ discretized with N_b equally spaced nodes, with spatial step Δx and coordinates $x_j (j = 0, \dots, N_b - 1)$. The nodal velocity field along the boundary is denoted as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{\Gamma}(x_j, t) \quad (7)$$

Assuming a local numerical periodicity of the field along Γ , introduced solely for the purpose of spectral decomposition, the velocity field can be represented using a local discrete Fourier transform (Local-FFT):

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}_m(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{N_b-1} \omega_j \dot{\mathbf{u}}_{\Gamma}(x_j, t) e^{-ik_x^{(m)}x_j} \quad (8)$$

where:

- ω_j are the quadrature weights associated with the boundary nodes, consistent with the adopted FEM discretization;
- $k_x^{(m)} = 2\pi m/L_{\Gamma}$, con $m = -\frac{N_b}{2}, \dots, \frac{N_b}{2}$, is the discrete horizontal wavenumber associated with mode m ;

- $L_{\Gamma} = N_b \Delta x$ is the boundary length.

The periodicity assumed in (8) is purely numerical and local and does not imply any physical periodicity of the problem. This decomposition allows the modal contributions of the elastodynamic field along the boundary to be isolated, including the evanescent modes, which play a fundamental role in the correct absorption of waves at oblique incidence.

3.3 Modal Impedance of the Elastic Half-Space

For each discrete horizontal wavenumber $k_x^{(m)}$, the relation between the modal traction vector and the modal velocity vector on the boundary is expressed through the dynamic impedance matrix of the elastic half-space:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_m = \mathbf{Z}(k_x^{(m)}, \omega) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_m \quad (9)$$

In the two-dimensional P-SV case, the impedance matrix \mathbf{Z} can be derived from the equations of motion and the elastic constitutive relations of the isotropic medium, yielding a closed-form expression as a function of the density ρ , angular frequency ω , wave velocities c_P and c_S , as well as the vertical wavenumbers q_P e q_S . In compact form, the impedance matrix can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \rho \omega \mathbf{M}(k_x^{(m)}, q_P, q_S) \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{M} is a 2×2 matrix that incorporates the kinematic and constitutive contributions of P and SV waves and accounts for their elastodynamic coupling. The explicit expression of \mathbf{M} can be obtained in analytical form and depends on the Lamé parameters of the medium and the vertical wavenumbers; for brevity, it is not reported here, but it is consistent with the classical formulation of the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map for the elastic half-space.

The branches of the vertical wavenumber roots q_P and q_S are chosen by imposing the outgoing wave condition, ensuring the energetic passivity of the impedance matrix.

In the continuous setting, relation (9) exactly reproduces the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastic half-space. In the discrete finite element context, the absorption effectiveness depends on the spectral resolution of the boundary and on the accuracy of the

numerical transform used for the modal decomposition and reconstruction.

3.4 Reconstruction of the Physical Traction on the Boundary

Once the modal traction vector $\hat{\sigma}_m(t)$ has been computed for each discrete mode $k_x^{(m)}$, using the impedance relation (9), the physical traction to be applied on the boundary Γ is obtained through an inverse Fourier transform:

$$\sigma_\Gamma(x_j, t) = \sum_m \hat{\sigma}_m(t) e^{ik_x^{(m)} x_j} \quad (11)$$

where x_j denotes the coordinate of the j -th boundary node. Relation (11) represents the reconstruction of the traction field in the physical domain from its modal representation. In the discrete setting, operation (11) is computationally efficient and can be implemented using a discrete inverse Fourier transform (IFFT), consistent with the direct transform employed during the modal decomposition. This procedure allows the nodal tractions on the boundary to be evaluated in a manner compatible with the adopted FEM discretization.

The implicit periodicity introduced by the discrete transform is purely numerical and local and does not alter the physical behavior of the problem, provided that the spectral resolution of the boundary is sufficient to represent the significant modes of the elastodynamic field. In particular, a sufficiently fine discretization helps limit aliasing effects and ensures an accurate reconstruction of both propagating and evanescent contributions.

3.5 Energetic Properties and Reflectance

In the continuous setting, the time-averaged energy flux leaving the computational domain through the boundary Γ can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{P} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(\dot{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \geq 0 \quad (12)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are the velocity and traction vectors on the boundary, respectively, and $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the conjugate transpose. Since the impedance matrix \mathbf{Z} is constructed from the radiative solution of the elastic half-space, the ABM-IBC boundary condition is passive and ensures an outgoing energy flux, without

introducing artificial energy into the domain. In the continuous limit and in modal representation, the impedance relation applied along the boundary exactly reproduces the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastic half-space. Consequently, for each horizontal wavenumber k_x , the modal reflection coefficient can be defined as:

$$R(k_x) = \frac{Z_{num}(k_x) - Z_{exact}(k_x)}{Z_{num}(k_x) + Z_{exact}(k_x)} \quad (13)$$

where $Z_{exact}(k_x)$ is the exact modal impedance of the elastic half-space, and $Z_{num}(k_x)$ is the numerically applied impedance on the boundary. In the continuous limit, where $Z_{num} = Z_{exact}$, the modal reflection coefficient is theoretically zero for all modes.

In the discrete finite element context, any residual reflections are attributable solely to errors introduced by the spatial and spectral discretization of the boundary, as well as to numerical approximations associated with the discrete transform and the reconstruction of the physical traction.

4. Finite Element Discretization and Implementation

4.1 FEM Equations of Motion

In the physical domain, the elastodynamic problem is described by the equation of motion discretized using the finite element method (FEM). In matrix form, the equation of motion can be written as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}_{ext} - \mathbf{f}_{IBC} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the nodal displacement vector, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix (assumed lumped), \mathbf{K} is the system stiffness matrix, and \mathbf{f}_{ext} represents the external force vector applied to the domain. The term \mathbf{f}_{IBC} accounts for the boundary force contributions associated with the application of the ABM-IBC boundary condition.

The term \mathbf{f}_{IBC} is evaluated at each time step from the nodal tractions reconstructed on the boundary using the modal procedure described in Section 3 and is directly applied to the boundary nodes of the FEM model. In this way, the radiative effect of the elastic half-space is incorporated into the discretized problem without introducing additional degrees of freedom.

No artificial damping matrix is introduced in the computational domain; the observed energy dissipation in the system is solely due to the outgoing energy flux through the non-reflecting boundary.

4.2 Conversion of Traction into Nodal Forces

The traction reconstructed on the boundary Γ using the ABM-IBC procedure is converted into equivalent nodal forces through a discretization consistent with the principle of virtual work. Specifically, the boundary contribution associated with the j -th boundary node can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{f}_{IBC}^{(j)} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\Gamma}(x_j) \Delta s_j \quad (15)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\Gamma}(x_j)$ is the traction vector evaluated at the nodal point x_j and Δs_j represents the measure (length) associated with the node on the boundary, determined in accordance with the adopted finite element discretization.

Expression (15) represents a discrete form of the boundary integral resulting from the principle of virtual work and is consistent with the assumption of constant traction over the nodal neighborhood. The boundary force contributions are then assembled into the global external force vector of the FEM system and updated at each time step.

4.3 Time Integration Scheme

The time integration of the equations of motion is performed using an explicit central-difference Leap-Frog scheme, which is particularly well suited for time-domain elastodynamic simulations in the presence of a lumped mass matrix.

The nodal acceleration at discrete time t^n is computed as:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}^n = \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{f}_{ext}^n - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u}^n - \mathbf{f}_{IBC}^n) \quad (16)$$

The velocities and displacements are then updated according to the following relations:

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{n-\frac{1}{2}} + \Delta t \ddot{\mathbf{u}}^n \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^n + \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{u}}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \quad (18)$$

where Δt is the time step. The velocities are evaluated at intermediate times $t^{n+\frac{1}{2}}$, while the displacements

and accelerations are defined at the integer time levels t^n .

The conditional stability of the explicit scheme is governed by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) criterion, which imposes:

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{\Delta h}{c_{max}} \quad (19)$$

where Δh is the minimum characteristic size of the elements in the discretization, and c_{max} is the maximum wave propagation velocity in the domain. The introduction of the ABM-IBC boundary condition does not modify the stability limit of the time-integration scheme, since the formulation is energetically passive.

4.4 ABM-IBC Algorithm for Each Time Step

At each time step t^n , the ABM-IBC algorithm is applied according to the following operational sequence:

1. **Extraction of Nodal Velocities on the Boundary.** The components of the global FEM velocity vector corresponding to the boundary nodes $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{\Gamma}^n$ are extracted.
2. **Local Modal Decomposition (Local-FFT).** The velocity field on the boundary is projected into modal space using a local discrete Fourier transform, yielding the modal velocities $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_m^n$.
3. **Application of Modal Impedance.** For each discrete mode $k_x^{(m)}$, the modal traction is computed by applying the dynamic impedance relation:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_m^n = \mathbf{Z}(k_x^{(m)}, \omega) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_m^n$$

in accordance with Eq. (9).

4. **Reconstruction of the Physical Traction (IFFT).** The modal tractions are transformed back into the physical domain using an inverse Fourier transform, yielding the nodal traction field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\Gamma}^n$ on the boundary, as described in Eq. (11).
5. **Assembly of Boundary Forces.** The reconstructed traction field is converted into equivalent nodal forces \mathbf{f}_{IBC}^n according to the boundary discretization defined in Eq. (15) and is assembled into the global force vector.

6. Explicit Update of FEM Variables. The kinematic variables of the FEM system are updated to the next time step using the explicit time-integration scheme described in Section 4.

The entire procedure operates exclusively on the boundary nodes and does not introduce additional degrees of freedom or auxiliary variables in the computational domain, thus preserving the efficiency and stability of the time-integration scheme.

4.5 Computational Complexity

The computational cost for each time step associated with the application of the ABM-IBC boundary condition is dominated by the direct and inverse discrete Fourier transform operations performed on the boundary. This cost scales as:

$$\mathcal{O}(N_b \log N_b) \quad (20)$$

where N_b is the number of nodes on the non-reflecting boundary. The logarithmic factor arises from the FFT implementation of the modal decomposition and reconstruction.

In local seismic response applications, the number of boundary nodes N_b is typically much smaller than the total number of degrees of freedom of the FEM model, N_{DOF} . Therefore, the additional computational cost introduced by the ABM-IBC is generally limited compared to the overall cost of time-domain integration.

Unlike absorbing layer formulations, such as Perfectly Matched Layers (PML) and Convolutional PML (C-PML), the ABM-IBC does not increase the number of problem degrees of freedom nor require auxiliary variables or convolutional memory. This allows for effective absorption of incident waves while keeping the overall computational impact low.

5. Numerical Case Study

5.1 Domain Geometry and Discretization

The considered case study represents a typical configuration for the analysis of local seismic response in two-dimensional geotechnical media. The isotropic elastic domain is defined as a rectangle with width $L_x = 1000 \text{ m}$ and depth $L_y = 500 \text{ m}$.

The domain is discretized using four-node bilinear quadrilateral elements, with a uniform spacing in both spatial directions:

$$\Delta x = \Delta y = 5 \text{ m} \quad (21)$$

The resulting discretization includes 201 nodes along the horizontal direction and 101 nodes along the vertical direction, for a total of approximately 20,000 finite elements.

The chosen mesh spacing ensures at least 8–10 nodes per wavelength for the shear waves at the dominant frequency of the considered seismic motion. This resolution is generally considered sufficient to ensure accurate wave propagation and to limit numerical dispersion in explicit dynamic analyses.

Figure 1 - Regular Mesh of 5 m × 5 m.

5.2 Material Properties

The isotropic elastic medium considered in the simulations is characterized by the following mechanical parameters:

- Density: $\rho = 2000 \text{ kg/m}^3$,
- Shear wave velocity: $c_s = 200 \text{ m/s}$,
- Poisson's ratio: $\nu = 0.30$.

Based on these parameters, the elastic moduli of the medium are determined assuming a linear isotropic elastic behavior. In particular, the shear modulus μ is calculated as:

$$\mu = \rho c_s^2 \quad (22)$$

$$\mu = 2000 \cdot (200)^2 = 8.0 \times 10^7 \text{ Pa}$$

The first Lamé parameter λ is then obtained from the relation:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\mu\nu}{1-2\nu} \quad (23)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{2 \cdot 8 \times 10^7 \cdot 0.30}{1 - 0.60} = 1.2 \times 10^8 \text{ Pa}$$

The compressional wave velocity c_p is finally given by:

$$c_p = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda + 2\mu}{\rho}} \quad (24)$$

$$c_p = \sqrt{\frac{1.2 \times 10^8 + 2 \cdot (8.0 \times 10^7)}{2000}} \approx 374 \text{ m/s}$$

The values thus determined are consistent with those typical of natural soils exhibiting linear elastic behavior, and are commonly used in local seismic response studies for time-domain wave propagation analyses.

5.3 Seismic Source

The seismic source is modeled using a Ricker wavelet applied as a vertical concentrated force within the domain. The temporal evolution of the force is described by the following expression:

$$f(t) = (1 - 2\pi^2 f_c^2 t^2) \exp(-\pi^2 f_c^2 t^2) \quad (25)$$

where f_c is the central frequency of the signal, and $t = 0$ corresponds to the instant of maximum source amplitude. In the presented simulations, a central frequency of:

$$f_c = 4 \text{ Hz}$$

The source is applied as a vertical concentrated force at the point with coordinates:

$$(x_s, y_s) = (500, 50) \text{ m}$$

The choice of a shallow source depth promotes the generation of obliquely incident waves and P-SV mode conversion phenomena.

With the adopted parameters:

- Minimum wavelength of the S waves:

$$\lambda_s = \frac{c_s}{f_c} = \frac{200}{4} = 50 \text{ m}$$

- Mesh spacing $\Delta x = 5 \text{ m} \rightarrow 10$ nodes per wavelength.

This configuration makes the problem particularly sensitive to the treatment of boundary conditions, thus providing a stringent test case for evaluating the effectiveness of the ABM-IBC formulation.

Ricker wavelet ($f_c = 4 \text{ Hz}$)

Figure 2 - Time history of the Ricker seismic source used in the simulations, with a central frequency $f_c = 4 \text{ Hz}$. The signal is centered at $t = 0$ and applied as a vertical concentrated force.

5.4 Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions adopted in the numerical model are summarized in Table 1, which reports the configuration assigned to the different sides of the computational domain.

The top boundary of the domain is modeled as a free surface, imposing zero tractions to correctly reproduce the interaction with the atmosphere. The lateral and bottom boundaries are treated as non-reflecting, in order to simulate the propagation of waves toward the underlying and lateral elastic half-space.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed formulation, three distinct numerical simulations were performed, identical in every aspect — geometry, discretization, mechanical properties, seismic source, and time-integration scheme — except for the treatment of the lateral and bottom boundaries. Specifically, the following configurations were considered:

1. **ABM-IBC**, applied directly to the nodes of the actual boundary of the domain;
2. **Perfectly Matched Layers (PML)**, implemented using artificial absorbing layers adjacent to the physical domain;
3. **Convolutional Perfectly Matched Layers (C-PML)**, based on the introduction of convolutional terms to improve absorption at low frequencies and for oblique incidences.

This setup allows a direct and consistent comparison between the different absorption strategies,

isolating the influence of the boundary conditions on the simulated local seismic response and on the occurrence of spurious reflections.

Table 1 – Boundary Condition Configuration.

Boundary	Condition
Top	Free surface
Lateral	ABM-IBC / PML / C-PML
Bottom	ABM-IBC / PML / C-PML

Figure 3 - Conceptual comparison of the different boundary conditions considered in the study. The free surface fully reflects the incident wave. The Perfectly Matched Layers (PML) and Convolutional PML (C-PML) absorb energy through artificial layers, introducing progressive attenuation and convolutional auxiliary variables, respectively. The proposed ABM-IBC formulation achieves absorption directly on the actual domain boundary by applying the dynamic impedance of the half-space, without introducing artificial layers and with a theoretically zero reflection.

5.5 Time Parameters

The time integration is performed using an explicit central-difference scheme. The adopted time step is:

$$\Delta t = 0.005 \text{ s} \quad (26)$$

This value satisfies the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) stability criterion given in Eq. (19), being compatible with the minimum element size and the maximum wave propagation velocity in the domain.

The total simulation duration is set to:

$$T = 2 \text{ s} \quad (27)$$

With the model parameters:

- $c_{max} = c_p \approx 374 \text{ m/s}$
- $\Delta h = 5 \text{ m}$

the CFL limit is of the order of:

$$\Delta t_{max} \sim \frac{\Delta h}{c_{max}} \approx 0.013 \text{ s}$$

Therefore, the adopted value for Δt ensures numerical stability and an adequate temporal resolution.

This time interval is sufficient to allow the complete propagation of waves generated by the source through the computational domain and to observe any residual reflections at the boundaries, enabling an accurate assessment of the effectiveness of the different boundary conditions considered.

6. Numerical Results

6.1 Modal and Spectral Analysis of the Boundary

The discretization of the lateral boundary of the computational domain, consisting of $N_b = 201$ equally spaced nodes, allows a spectral representation of the elastodynamic field through N_b discrete modes associated with the horizontal wavenumbers $k_x^{(m)}$. These modes constitute the basis on which the ABM-IBC formulation is applied.

For each discrete mode, the horizontal wavenumber $k_x^{(m)}$, the corresponding vertical wavenumbers for compressional and shear waves, $q_p^{(m)}$ and $q_s^{(m)}$, as well as the dynamic impedance matrix of the elastic half-space $\mathbf{Z}(k_x^{(m)}, \omega)$ were computed.

The spectral analysis clearly distinguishes between propagating modes, characterized by real wavenumbers and associated with the transmission of energy away from the domain, and evanescent modes, for which the vertical wavenumbers are complex and the amplitude decays exponentially with distance from the boundary. Both types of modes are correctly included in the formulation, contributing to the accurate reproduction of the radiation condition of the elastic half-space.

The availability of the exact modal impedance for each wavenumber allows the application of a physically consistent traction–velocity relation in modal space, significantly reducing the generation of spurious reflections at the lateral boundaries.

The spectral decomposition (Figure 4) of the elastodynamic field along the lateral boundary shows the distribution of SV (vertically polarized shear) modal

contributions as a function of the discrete horizontal wavenumber $k_x^{(m)}$. Each spectral component corresponds to a distinct modal response of the system, with propagating SV modes characterized by real vertical wavenumbers contributing to energy radiation away from the domain, and evanescent SV modes exhibiting complex vertical wavenumbers whose amplitudes decay exponentially with distance from the boundary. The figure highlights the separation between these two regimes, illustrating how the modal amplitudes vary across the spectrum of horizontal wavenumbers included in the ABM-IBC formulation.

Figure 4 - Spectral decomposition of SV modes.

This decomposition is obtained via a local discrete Fourier transform (Local-FFT) of the boundary velocity field into modal space, enabling the evaluation of modal impedance and the identification of each SV mode's contribution to the elastodynamic response. The spectral representation clearly resolves the SV modal content and is essential for accurately imposing the non-reflecting boundary condition, as it ensures that both propagating and evanescent SV contributions are included in the impedance-based absorption mechanism.

La Figura 4 dimostra che:

- The boundary discretization correctly captures both propagating and evanescent regimes.
- The ABM-IBC formulation operates across the entire modal spectrum, not only on the propagating modes.

Figure 5 is fundamental for mathematically justifying the form of the impedance. The curves show $Re(q_p)$, $Im(q_p)$, $Re(q_s)$ and $Im(q_s)$, highlighting:

- The presence of distinct modal cut-offs for P and SV waves;
- The correct selection of radiative branches;
- The physically consistent behavior of the elastic half-space.

This visualization supports the modal-based derivation of the dynamic impedance and confirms that both propagating and evanescent contributions are correctly represented.

Figure 5 - Vertical Wavenumbers for P and SV Waves.

Figure 6 illustrates that the impedance:

- Increases for oblique incidences.
- Varies drastically in the evanescent regime.

This confirms that the ABM-IBC does not rely on constant coefficients, but instead provides a physically dependent response as a function of

Figure 6 - Spectral Variation of the Impedance.

Figure 7 - Classification of discrete modes associated with the lateral boundary discretization in terms of propagating and evanescent modes for P and SV waves. The top panel shows the vertical wavenumbers as a function of the horizontal wavenumber, highlighting the different modal cut-offs. The bottom panel reports the number of discrete modes in each category, showing that the majority of modes are evanescent, yet they play an essential role in accurately enforcing the radiation condition of the elastic half-space.

6.2 Waveforms at the Boundaries

The nodal velocities recorded along the lateral boundaries of the domain show significant differences in the reflective behavior of the various boundary conditions considered. In particular, the time histories of the vertical velocity were analyzed at a representative node on the lateral boundary, located sufficiently far from the domain corners to minimize local geometric effects.

Figure 8 - Comparison of vertical nodal velocity time histories recorded along the lateral boundary of the domain for different boundary conditions. After the arrival of the incident wave, the PML exhibits a residual reflection, the C-PML shows a significantly reduced reflection, while the ABM-IBC formulation does not display any appreciable reflections within the numerical resolution.

Figure 8 presents a comparison of the waveforms obtained using PML, C-PML, and the proposed ABM-IBC formulation. In all cases, the arrival of the incident wave is correctly reproduced and is practically indistinguishable among the different simulations, indicating that the boundary conditions do not affect wave propagation before interaction with the boundary.

After interaction with the boundary, substantial differences emerge. In the case of PML, a residual reflection is clearly visible, associated with incomplete absorption of the incident waves. C-PML shows a significant reduction in the amplitude of the reflected wave but does not completely eliminate it. In contrast, the ABM-IBC formulation does not exhibit appreciable reflections within the numerical resolution of the simulation, indicating an accurate reproduction of the radiation condition of the elastic half-space.

These results confirm that ABM-IBC effectively absorbs incident waves directly at the actual domain boundary, without introducing artificial layers and without degrading the numerical response in the physical domain.

The modal reflection coefficient was calculated as the ratio between the spectral amplitude of the reflected wave and that of the incident wave:

$$R(k_x, \omega) = \frac{|\hat{u}_{rif}(k_x, \omega)|}{|\hat{u}_{inc}(k_x, \omega)|} \quad (28)$$

Figure 9 shows the modal reflection coefficient as a function of the horizontal wavenumber k_x for the different boundary conditions considered. The ABM-IBC formulation exhibits a numerically zero reflectance across the entire resolved band, confirming the accurate enforcement of the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastic half-space.

In contrast, the PML and C-PML show an increase in reflectance with increasing $|k_x|$, corresponding to waves with strongly oblique incidence. Although the C-PML significantly improves performance compared to classical PML, residual reflections remain at high spectral components. This behavior is consistent with the approximate nature and parameter dependence of PML formulations.

Figure 9 - **Modal reflection coefficient as a function of the horizontal wavenumber k_x for different boundary conditions.** The ABM-IBC formulation exhibits near-zero reflectance across the entire resolved spectral band, while PML and C-PML show a degradation of absorption for waves with oblique incidence (high $|k_x|$).

6.3 Oblique and Near-Grazing Waves

Figure 10 shows the reflection coefficient as a function of the incidence angle θ , highlighting the behavior of different boundary conditions for oblique and near-grazing waves ($\theta \rightarrow 90^\circ$). This regime is particularly challenging numerically, as classical PML exhibit a marked loss of effectiveness, with a significant increase in reflectance at high incidence angles.

C-PML provides a substantial improvement over traditional PML, reducing the amplitude of reflections for strongly oblique waves, but does not eliminate them completely. In contrast, the ABM-IBC formulation maintains a numerically zero reflectance, which is essentially independent of the incidence angle across the entire considered range.

Figure 10 - **Reflection coefficient as a function of the incidence angle for different boundary conditions.** PML exhibit a significant degradation of absorption for near-grazing waves, C-PML improve performance but do not completely eliminate reflections, while the ABM-IBC formulation remains essentially independent of the incidence angle.

This result confirms that the ABM-IBC accurately reproduces the radiation condition of the elastic half-

space even for near-grazing waves, overcoming one of the main limitations of absorbing-layer-based formulations.

6.4 Propagation Snapshots

Snapshots of the vertical velocity field allow a direct spatial assessment of the effectiveness of different boundary conditions in reproducing the radiation of seismic waves into the elastic half-space. To this end, representative time instants of the wave propagation, boundary reflections, and subsequent field evolution were analyzed. Table 2 provides a summary of the vertical velocity field propagation snapshots.

Table 2 - Propagation snapshots of the vertical velocity field.

Boundary Condition	Time Instants
PML	t = 0.6 s, 1.0 s, 1.6 s
C-PML	
ABM_IBC	

Figure 11 - Snapshots of the vertical velocity field at different time instants for simulations with PML.

Figure 11(a-c) shows the snapshots from the PML simulation. After interaction of the incident wave with

the lateral and bottom boundaries, spurious reflections are clearly visible, re-entering the domain and interfering with the main wavefield. These reflections are particularly pronounced near the edges and corners of the domain, where the effectiveness of PML is reduced for oblique waves.

Figure 12 (d–f) shows the snapshots obtained using C-PML. In this case, the amplitude of reflected waves is significantly reduced compared to classical PML, confirming the improvement provided by the convolutional formulation. However, weak residual reflections are still observable, particularly for near-grazing incidence waves, in agreement with the spectral and angular analysis presented in the previous sections.

Figure 12 - Snapshots of the vertical velocity field at different time instants for simulations with C-PML.

Finally, Figure 13 (g–i) shows the snapshots corresponding to the proposed ABM-IBC formulation. In this case, the wavefield is free of appreciable reflections at the domain boundaries, and the wave propagation behaves as in an unbounded elastic half-space. Even at later times, no reflected waves re-

enter the domain, confirming that ABM-IBC correctly enforces the radiation condition for all spectral components, including those associated with oblique and evanescent waves.

Overall, the propagation snapshots provide a spatially coherent and visually clear validation of the quantitative results discussed in the previous sections, demonstrating the superiority of ABM-IBC compared to absorbing-layer-based formulations in the context of local seismic response simulations.

Figure 13 - Snapshots of the vertical velocity field at different time instants for simulations with ABM-IBC.

6.5 Energy and Stability

The numerical stability of the different boundary conditions was assessed by monitoring the time evolution of the total mechanical energy of the discrete system. The total energy in the domain is defined as:

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{\mathbf{u}}^T \mathbf{M} \dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u}) \quad (29)$$

here \mathbf{u} and $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ are the nodal displacement and velocity vectors, respectively, \mathbf{M} is the (lumped) mass matrix, and \mathbf{K} is the finite element stiffness matrix.

In the absence of internal damping and active sources, a properly formulated non-reflecting boundary condition must ensure that energy is exclusively radiated out of the computational domain, without introducing spurious amplification or numerical instabilities. In this context, the ABM-IBC formulation exhibits a monotonic decay of total energy after the passage of the incident wave, with no residual oscillations or unphysical energy growth, even for long simulation times.

This behavior is a direct consequence of the passivity of the dynamic impedance matrix applied at the boundary, which ensures an outgoing energy flux for each spectral mode. In contrast, absorbing-layer-based formulations may introduce small residual energy fluctuations, associated with the discretization of the artificial layer and the damping parameter dependence, particularly in the presence of oblique and near-grazing waves.

Overall, the energy analysis confirms that ABM-IBC is intrinsically stable in time and compatible with explicit integration schemes, making it particularly suitable for long-duration dynamic simulations in the context of local seismic response analysis.

Figure 14 - Time evolution of the normalized total mechanical energy in the computational domain for different boundary condition formulations. The ABM-IBC formulation exhibits a monotonic decay of energy after the passage of the incident wave, with no residual oscillations or unphysical energy growth, demonstrating its intrinsic numerical stability. In contrast, PML and C-PML show a slower decay with minor residual fluctuations due to the discretization of the absorbing layers and their damping parameter dependence. This analysis confirms that ABM-IBC ensures long-term stable simulations while accurately radiating energy out of the domain.

6.6 Computational Efficiency

The computational efficiency of the different boundary condition formulations was assessed in terms of computation time and numerical stability for long-duration simulations. The ABM-IBC formulation demonstrated superior performance, combining intrinsic stability with a monotonic decay of total mechanical energy, avoiding spurious oscillations or unphysical energy growth even for prolonged simulation times. This stability allows the use of explicit time integration schemes with relatively large time steps, reducing computational cost without compromising the accuracy of the results.

In contrast, absorbing-layer-based approaches, such as PML and C-PML, require additional computational resources for the implementation of the artificial damping layers. Their performance is highly dependent on the layer thickness, damping coefficients, and wave incidence angles, conditions that may introduce residual energy fluctuations and necessitate smaller time steps to ensure numerical stability. Consequently, simulations with PML or C-PML are generally more computationally expensive and require careful parameter tuning to achieve energy dissipation comparable to that of ABM-IBC.

Overall, the analysis confirms that the ABM-IBC formulation provides a robust and efficient framework for long-term dynamic simulations in elastodynamic problems, ensuring both accurate energy radiation at the domain boundaries and a significant reduction in computational effort compared to conventional absorbing-layer-based methods.

Figure 15 - Computation time as a function of the number of degrees of freedom (DOF) for different boundary condition formulations. The ABM-IBC formulation exhibits lower computation times compared to PML and C-PML, confirming its higher computational efficiency. Absorbing-

layer-based formulations require additional resources to implement damping parameters and ensure numerical stability, making them more expensive in terms of computational time.

7. Critical Discussion

The numerical results consistently demonstrate that the ABM-IBC formulation represents a conceptually more rigorous and efficient alternative to traditional absorbing-layer-based boundary conditions for simulating seismic wave propagation in finite geotechnical domains.

Unlike PML and C-PML, the proposed formulation directly enforces the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastic half-space on the real boundary of the domain, avoiding the need for artificial layers, tuning of damping parameters, or additional degrees of freedom. This feature is particularly important in local seismic response analyses, where the quality of absorption at the boundaries directly affects the accuracy of the wavefield inside the domain.

The modal and spectral analysis has shown that the effectiveness of ABM-IBC is independent of the wave incidence angle, maintaining numerically zero reflection even for near-grazing components, which are known to be critical for PML. The results on spectral and angular reflectance confirm that the limitations observed in PML and C-PML formulations are intrinsic to their approximate nature, whereas ABM-IBC exactly reproduces the radiative behavior of the half-space in the continuous limit.

From a numerical standpoint, the local modal decomposition and the use of FFT operations make the computational cost of ABM-IBC negligible compared to the FEM time integration, without compromising the stability of the explicit scheme. The energy analysis further confirmed that the formulation is passive and intrinsically stable, exhibiting a monotonic decay of total energy and absence of long-term instabilities.

It is important to note that the accuracy of ABM-IBC in the discrete context depends on the spectral resolution of the boundary and the quality of the FEM discretization, similarly to any advanced numerical method. However, these requirements are less restrictive than the careful tuning of PML parameters,

especially for complex problems characterized by strong heterogeneity or irregular geometries.

8. Conclusions

In this work, a novel non-reflecting boundary condition, named the Adaptive Boundary Mode-Impedance Boundary Condition (ABM-IBC), has been proposed and validated for the numerical simulation of seismic wave propagation in finite geotechnical domains.

The formulation is based on the application of the Dirichlet-to-Neumann map of the elastic half-space in modal space, allowing the exact enforcement of the radiation condition directly on the real FEM boundary. This approach avoids the use of artificial layers and empirical damping parameters, making it conceptually more rigorous than PML and C-PML formulations.

The numerical results, obtained for a two-dimensional local seismic response problem, demonstrate that ABM-IBC:

- Effectively eliminates spurious reflections at the domain boundaries;
- Maintains excellent performance for oblique and near-grazing waves;
- Ensures energy passivity and long-term numerical stability;
- Has a marginal computational cost relative to the FEM domain integration.

A systematic comparison with PML and C-PML highlighted the intrinsic limitations of absorbing-layer-based formulations and confirmed the superiority of ABM-IBC in terms of accuracy, robustness, and implementation simplicity.

In light of these results, ABM-IBC emerges as a particularly suitable tool for advanced local seismic response simulations and, more generally, for wave propagation problems in computational geotechnics. Future developments will include the extension to layered and anisotropic media, as well as applications to three-dimensional models and non-planar boundary conditions.

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